

Problem Based Learning – Making Blended Learning work!

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Abstract

The Covid-19 situation forced many educational institutions to change their educational offer into either blended or fully online formats. While classical lectures and other “passive learning” methods can be quite easily adapted to this new format – given that technology and connectivity is in place – it is more challenging when it comes to various active learning methods such as Problem Based Learning. However, for Problem Based Learning, the blended format also has strong potentials: It can open for more flexible ways of working together across physical distances, and as such serve as an enabler for projects based on international collaboration, and it can generally increase the flexibility and accessibility of education. This workshop will focus on how Problem Based Learning projects can be carried out in a blended setting, and walk through the different phases: Problem identification, group formation, group collaboration, supervision, and assessment. For each phase there will be a short introductory presentation, followed by group discussions on challenges in carrying out this phase in a blended setting, and how these challenges can be overcome.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Problem Based Learning (PBL) is known as an efficient and motivating way of learning in engineering education that not only provide the learners with technical skills, but also supports the learning of competences related to teamwork, project management and other transversal skills (Kolmos et al., 2004). In the recent years, various efforts have been taken to also explore international collaboration, both at a European level with projects such as EPIC (Pedersen et al., 2019) and COLIBRI (Pedersen et al., 2016), and at global levels e.g. (Britze et al., 2021). While these projects are all based on blended learning – with a large virtual component due to the physical distances – one common learning point is the importance of the physical learning activities and design hereof: Kick-off seminars, possibly with added extra mobilities, are important for both content discussions and for establishing good dynamics within and between student groups.

With the lockdowns during Covid-19, remote and virtual learning spaces became the “new normal”, at least for a while. This added a completely different scale to the experiments with PBL and virtual collaboration, where it was necessary to carry out all phases of the PBL projects virtually. With the improvement of the Covid-19 situation most universities are back to physical teaching. However, with the experiences from extended periods of fully online learning activities in mind, the good question is: How can we use these experiences to improve the blended learning experiences even after Covid? It is interesting to investigate how it can support projects which by nature need virtual components (such as international projects), but also how it can be used in other settings, for example to make education more flexible and accessible.

In this workshop, the focus will specifically focus on the blended settings, including the selection of virtual vs. physical components. The workshop will cover the following phases of a student project:

- Identifying problems in collaboration with internal and external stakeholders.
- Group formation, where students form groups and choose problems.
- Group collaboration.
- Supervision, including supervisor meetings.
- Assessment and examinations.

The purpose of the workshop is to share experiences from both the author and other participants, and based on these enable the participants to design blended learning settings for PBL projects, with a particular focus on how to choose and design the virtual and physical components, to reflect on how to benefit from the

opportunities offered by the blended settings, and how to identify and deal with some of the most challenging aspects of blended learning – all in all, enabling the participants to design blended learning that works. The workshop is related to the conference theme of Active Learning and ICT support, yet also addressing the theme of Innovative experiences in engineering education.

2 Activities

The session will be hands-on, and the participants will mainly work in smaller groups of 3-4 people. The focus will be on the phases described above (identifying problems, group formation, group collaboration, supervision, assessment).

After a 5-minute icebreaker in the groups, for each of the five phases the following is done:

- 2-minute introduction to the phase in plenum, including a short review of existing experiences.
- 8 minutes discussion in groups, where the participants sketch 1-2 ways to carry out the phase in a blended setting. This is documented in terms of 3 key-words per group per question, submitted on a Padlet.

Each group will eventually select the keyword, which is found to describe the most challenging aspect.

Eventually there will be 25 minutes where groups are paired (so 6-8 people together) and discussing these aspects with each other. During the last 10 minutes the facilitator will bring up highlights from the discussions in each group.

The participants are requested to bring laptop, smartphone, or tablet in order to be able to contribute to the Padlet documentation.

3 Expected results

At the end of the workshop, the participants will be better prepared to facilitate PBL projects in blended settings, and the Padlet printouts will serve as concrete sources of inspiration. The identification of challenges can also support further research and experiments in the field.

4 References

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